

An Attempt to Account Quantitatively for the Electroviscous Behaviour of an Association Colloid

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-790 009

Manuscript received 12 December 1978, accepted 6 June 1979

Smoluchowski's equation for electroviscous effect has been modified by the author. The modified equation has been applied to account for the viscous behaviour of the micelles of sodium dodecyl sulfate solution under different experimental conditions and has been found satisfactory.

It has been shown by the author in previous publications¹⁻³ that Smoluchowski's⁴ equation has to be modified to account quantitatively for the electroviscous behaviour of colloidal electrolytes and ampholytes. In this paper it will be shown how the modified equation can be used to account quantitatively for the electroviscous behaviour of an association colloid such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (NaDS). The modified equation may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = \frac{Kv}{100} \left[1 + \left(\frac{D\zeta^2}{2\pi} \right) \frac{(C+K_0)}{\eta_0 a^2 (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1)} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_{sp} denotes the specific viscosity of the colloidal solution, C , the colloid concentration in grams per 100 ml of the solution, K , the Einstein constant equal to 2.5 for spherical particles, v , the specific volume of the colloidal material, ζ , the electrokinetic potential of the particles of radius a , and D , η_0 and λ_1 denote respectively the dielectric constant, viscosity and specific conductivity of the dispersion medium, K_0 , a constant independent of C , the colloid concentration, but it may or may not vary with the concentration of an added strong electrolyte and λ_s is a characteristic constant for a pure colloidal electrolyte and may be interpreted to represent the specific conductivity associated with a unit area of the diffuse electrical double layer of a particle at the plane of contact with an electrode of the conductivity cell.

Simplified forms of equation (1) according to experimental conditions :

Putting $K_1 = \frac{Kv}{100}$ and $A_0 = \frac{1}{\eta_0 a^2} \left(\frac{D}{2\pi} \right)^2$ equation (1)

may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K_1 \left[1 + \frac{A_0 \zeta^2 (C+K_0)}{\lambda_s (C+K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s)} \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

In a sol highly purified by dialysis λ_1 is usually smaller than λ_s , therefore, K_0 is greater than $K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s$.

Under this condition, if C is very small compared to K_0 , it can be neglected in the numerator of equation (2) which then assumes the following form :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K_1 \left[1 + \frac{A_0 \zeta^2 K_0}{\lambda_s (C+K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s)} \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

Under this condition if C alone is decreased then η_{sp}/C increases as the other terms remain constant.

In those sols, however, in which λ_1 is greater than λ_s , so that $K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s$ is greater than K_0 , then so long as C is very small compared to $K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s$, it can be neglected in the denominator of equation (2) which then assumes the following form :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_{sp}/C &= K_1 \left[1 + \frac{A_0 \zeta^2 (C+K_0)}{K_0 \lambda_1} \right] \\ &= K_1 [1 + A_1 + BC] \quad \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

where $A_1 = A_0 \zeta^2 / \lambda_1$ and $B = A_0 \zeta^2 / K_0 \lambda_1$

Now if C alone is increased η_{sp}/C should increase linearly with C so long as the latter is negligible compared to $K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s$. It is to be noted that all the aforesaid equations deal only with the primary electroviscous effect.

It also follows from equation (4) that $A_1/B = K_0$ and hence the effect of added electrolyte on K_0 can be ascertained.

Verifications of the equations :

The viscometric behaviour of sols of sodium dodecyl sulfate in water has been carefully investigated by Kushner, Duncan and Hoffmann⁵. They have preferred to use the term "monomer saturation concentration" instead of "critical micelle concentration" for reasons stated in their paper⁵. All sodium dodecyl sulfate (NaDS) added to the solution above the "monomer saturation concentration"

becomes micelles. Some of their data are recorded in Table 1, where column 1 contains the values of the constants K_1 , A_1 and B of equation (4) and the concentrations of NaCl added and column 2 contains the values of C in grams per 100 ml of solution. Since the monomer saturation concentration of (NaDS) is 0.281 grams per 100 ml therefore, λ_1 should be relatively high and greater than λ_s . Under this condition equation (4) should hold good so long as C is very small compared to $K_0\lambda_1/\lambda_s$.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF η_{sp}/C WITH C OF (NaDS) SOLS AT 23°C

Miscellaneous	C	Values of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
NaCl—Nil Eqn. used (4) $K_1=0.033$ $A_1=0.97$ $B=1.90$ $A_1/B=0.51$	0.00 0.019 0.119 0.219 0.319	0.065 0.068 0.071 0.079 0.085	0.065 0.066 0.072 0.079 0.085
NaCl—0.01N Eqn. used (4) $K_1=0.033$ $A_1=0.46$ $B=0.91$ $A_1/B=0.51$	0.00 0.036 0.196 0.296 0.396 0.496	0.048 0.051 0.054 0.057 0.060 0.063	0.048 0.051 0.054 0.057 0.060 0.063
NaCl—0.02N Eqn. used (4) $K_1=0.033$ $A_1=0.35$ $B=0.5$ $A_1/B=0.70$	0.00 0.089 0.189 0.289 0.389 0.489	0.045 0.048 0.047 0.049 0.050 0.051	0.045 0.046 0.047 0.049 0.050 0.052
NaCl—0.03N Eqn. used (4) $K_1=0.033$ $A_1=0.24$ $B=0.45$ $A_1/B=0.53$	0.00 0.064 0.114 0.264 0.364 0.464	0.041 0.042 0.043 0.044 0.046 0.047	0.041 0.042 0.043 0.045 0.046 0.048
NaCl—0.04N Eqn. used (4) $K_1=0.033$ $A_1=0.18$ $B=0.36$ $A_1/B=0.50$	0.00 0.081 0.181 0.281 0.381 0.481	0.039 0.040 0.041 0.042 0.043 0.044	0.039 0.040 0.041 0.042 0.043 0.045

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the observed values of η_{sp}/C for different values of C agree well with those calculated from equation (4). When C alone is varied A_1 and B each remain constant, but they vary when the concentration of added NaCl is altered. The constant K_1 is, however, not affected by the variation of either C or NaCl concentration and its value remains equal to 0.033 throughout. Since equation (4) deals only with the primary electroviscous effect, therefore, variation of η_{sp}/C with C is to be attributed to this effect alone.

It is also to be noted that A_1/B , which is equal to K_0 , lie between 0.50 and 0.53 at NaCl concentrations equal to 0, 0.01 N, 0.03 N and 0.04 N so it may be treated as constant within the aforesaid range of NaCl concentration. It may be pointed

out that the ratio of A_1/B is very sensitive to experimental error involved in the determination of η_{sp}/C and the monomer saturation concentration. Therefore, the high value of $A_1/B=0.70$ observed at 0.02N NaCl concentration may be attributed to some accidental experimental error. This point will be discussed further in a later section.

Kushner, Duncan and Hoffmann⁵ used the following empirical equation to represent the variation of η_{sp}/C with C observed by them

$$\eta_{sp}/C = [\eta] + D'C \quad \dots (4a)$$

where $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic viscosity and D' a constant. The term $D'C$ in equation (4a) is attributed to secondary electroviscous effect caused by the collision of the colloidal particles. They⁵ have observed that $[\eta]$ decreases as the concentration of the added NaCl is increased and reaches a limiting value slightly less than 0.035 at a sufficiently high concentration of NaCl. No quantitative treatment of the variation observed has been attempted by them. Such a treatment has, therefore, been attempted in the next section.

Variation of η_{sp}/C with NaCl concentration at constant C :

Let S denote the concentration of NaCl added, $[\eta_{sp}/C]_s$, the reduced viscosity of the (NaDS) sol containing NaCl of concentration S and $[\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow 0}$ that of the sol without any NaCl. Let the ratio $[\eta_{sp}/C]_s : [\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow 0}$ be denoted by R . Then an equation connecting R with S may be derived from equation (2) in the following way.

Let ζ change to $\zeta(1-as)$ and λ_1 change to $\lambda_1(1+hS)$ as the concentration S of added NaCl changes from zero to S . Now putting $A = A_0(C + K_0)$ in equation (2) we may write as follows :—

$$\begin{aligned} R &= [\eta_{sp}/C]_s : [\eta_{sp}/C]_0 \\ &= K_1 \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2(1-as)^2}{C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1(1+hS)} \right] : K_1 \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2}{C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{B + (K_0\lambda_1h - 2Aa\zeta^2)S}{H + K_0\lambda_1hS} \times \frac{H}{B} \right] \\ &= 1 - \frac{mS}{m_0 + S} \quad \dots (5) \end{aligned}$$

where terms in $(S)^2$ have been neglected and

$$\begin{aligned} B &= (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1 + A\zeta^2), \quad H = (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1), \\ m &= \left[\frac{(K_0\lambda_1h/H) - (K_0\lambda_1h - 2Aa\zeta^2)/B}{(K_0\lambda_1h)/H} \right] \end{aligned}$$

and $m_0 = H/K_0\lambda_1h$.

In equation (5) m and m_0 are constants since all the terms contained in them remain constant when S alone is varied.

It follows from equation (5) that when S approaches infinity then $R = [\eta_{sp}/C]_s / [\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow 0} = 1 - m$. Therefore $[\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow \infty} = R[\eta_{sp}/C]_0 = (1 - m)[\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow 0}$... (5a)

Using the data recorded in Table 1, η_{sp}/C versus C are plotted for different values of S. From these plots, at any desired C, values of η_{sp}/C for different values of S are found. These are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF R WITH NaCl CONCENTRATION, S

Miscellaneous	S	η_{sp}/C	Values of R	
			Observed	Calculated
C=0 Eqn. (5) m=0.485 m ₀ =0.0085	0.0	0.065	1.0	1.0
	0.01N	0.048	0.738	0.738
	0.02N	0.045	0.683	0.660
	0.03N	0.041	0.681	0.625
	0.04N	0.039	0.600	0.600
Infinity	—	—	—	0.515
C=0.1 Eqn. (5) m=0.531 m ₀ =0.0087	0.0	0.071	1.0	1.0
	0.01N	0.051	0.718	0.716
	0.02N	0.046	0.648	0.630
	0.03N	0.042	0.592	0.588
	0.04N	0.040	0.563	0.565
Infinity	—	—	—	0.469
C=0.2 Eqn. (5) m=0.568 m ₀ =0.0039	0.0	0.077	1.0	1.0
	0.01N	0.054	0.701	0.700
	0.02N	0.048	0.625	0.607
	0.03N	0.043	0.559	0.562
	0.04N	0.041	0.533	0.536
Infinity	—	—	—	0.432
C=0.3 Eqn. (5) m=0.61 m ₀ =0.0091	0.0	0.084	1.0	1.0
	0.01N	0.057	0.680	0.681
	0.02N	0.049	0.583	0.581
	0.03N	0.045	0.536	0.532
	0.04N	0.042	0.500	0.503
Infinity	—	—	—	0.390
C=0.4 Eqn. (5) m=0.64 m ₀ =0.0093	0.0	0.090	1.0	1.0
	0.01N	0.060	0.667	0.668
	0.02N	0.051	0.587	0.563
	0.03N	0.046	0.511	0.511
	0.04N	0.043	0.478	0.481
Infinity	—	—	—	0.360

In Table 3 the values of C and $[\eta_{sp}/C]_{s \rightarrow 0}$ are recorded in the first and second rows. The third and fourth rows contain, for S approaching infinity, the values of R and $[\eta_{sp}/C]_s$.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF K₁ i.e. $[\eta_{sp}/C]_s$ WHEN S → INFINITY

C	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
$[\eta_{sp}/C]_0$	0.065	0.071	0.077	0.084	0.090
R for S → Infinity	0.515	0.469	0.432	0.390	0.360
$[\eta_{sp}/C]_s$ for S → Infinity	0.0335	0.0333	0.0333	0.0328	0.0324

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 2 that the values of R calculated by using equation (5) agree well with those observed except for S equal to 0.02N and C lying between 0.0 and

0.2. When S=0.02N and C=0.0 the calculated value of R is 0.660 while the observed value is 0.683. The value of η_{sp}/C which corresponds to R=0.660 is 0.043 and that which corresponds to R=0.683 is 0.045 and such difference in the values of η_{sp}/C is within the limits of experimental error. It may, however, be pointed out that for S=0.02N the value of A₁/B recorded in Table 1 may be 0.53 or 0.70 according as η_{sp}/C is taken equal to 0.043 or 0.045.

The assumptions involved in the derivation of eqn. (5) are that ζ decreases and λ_1 increases as the concentration, S of the added NaCl is increased. When S approaches infinity, ζ decreases to almost zero and λ_1 acquires a very high value, consequently in equation (4), A₁ and B each becomes almost zero. Under this condition η_{sp}/C becomes equal to K₁ which as shown in Table 1 is 0.033.

The data recorded in Table 3 show that when S approaches infinity the value of η_{sp}/C calculated by using equation (5a) becomes constant independent of C and its average is 0.033 which, as it should be, is the same as that of K₁.

It has been pointed out by Kushner, Duncan and Hoffmann⁵ that $K_1 = 0.033 = \frac{2.5}{(\alpha)1000}$ when α , the density, of the micelles of sodium dodecyl sulfate is put equal to 0.75 which is nearly the same as that of liquid dodecane. As the limiting value of the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ of the (NaDS) sol at high NaCl concentration has been found to be 0.035 which is quite close to 0.033 so they⁵ have suggested that the micelles of (NaDS) are spherical in shape. The value of K₁=0.033 found from the equations (4) and (5a) supports the view, regarding spherical shape, expressed by the aforesaid authors⁵.

It may also be noted that the value of m₀ recorded in Table 2 increases as C increases. It follows from the derivation of equation (5) that $m_0 = (\lambda_0/K_0\lambda_1h)C + (1/h)$. Therefore, under conditions in which equation (5) holds good, m₀ must vary with C.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Dr. K. Chakravarti for kindly supplying photocopy of some publications.

References

1. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 881.
2. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 1066.
3. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 694.
4. M. VON SMOLUCHOWSKI, *Kolloid Z.*, 1916, **18**, 194.
5. L. M. KUSHNER, B. C. DUNCAN and J. I. HOFFMANN, *J. Research NBS*, 1952, **49**, 85.